

Security Assurance in Modern IoT Systems

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Abstract—Modern distributed systems consist of a multi-layer architecture of IoT, edge, and cloud nodes. Together, they are revolutionizing our lives, bringing intelligence to existing processes (e.g., smart grids) and enabling novel, efficient and effective processes (e.g., remote surgery). This transition however does not come without drawbacks, due to the ever-increasing reliance on devices whose security and safety are, at least, questionable. In this context, research is in its infancy, struggling to adapt successful practices applied, for instance, in cloud systems. Security of modern IoT systems still relies on old-fashioned approaches, mostly static assessments considering only very specific parts of the target system, rather than assessing the system as a whole. In this paper, we put forward the idea of security assurance for IoT, as a higher-level assurance process evaluating the target system at different layers and different moments of its lifecycle, then implemented by a flexible assurance framework. The quality of our approach is evaluated in a real-world smart lighting system.

Index Terms—Assurance, Cloud-Edge, IoT, Security

I. INTRODUCTION

Novel networking paradigms such as Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) and 5G, together with novel computing paradigms such as edge computing, are revolutionizing the way IT services are engineered, delivered, and utilized. The confluence of these technologies point to Internet of Things (IoT) systems that no longer consist of “smart things” only, but rather embrace multi-tiered systems where data collected by sensors on the field are analyzed with low latency at the edge, and are the basis for further optimization at the cloud. These systems provide unmatched simplifications to our lives, from the delivery of novel services such as remote healthcare, to the optimization of existing ones, such as smart grid. Altogether, the estimated economic impact of IoT by 2025 is in the range of 2.7 to 6.2 trillion dollars [1].

The price we pay is however not negligible, with increasing risk of safety, security, and privacy, due to the pervasiveness of these systems as well as the interplay with their physical counterparts. Continuous assessment of the behavior of such systems becomes therefore fundamental. Security assurance is one

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of the preferred solutions in this regards, providing processes and corresponding frameworks evaluating the compliance of IT systems with respect to user-defined requirements. Security assurance has been consistently applied in service and cloud-based systems [2], [3], [4], yet it is in its infancy when it comes to IoT systems. Static and punctual assessments have been the preferred approach, but no longer are a viable option [5]. Some preliminary solutions have been defined [5], [6], [7], [8], but alternatives are still lacking. In general, they consider low-level details and traditional CIA properties (*Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability*) only, or provide a system overview which is too abstract to be really useful.

In this paper, we build on the security assurance framework in [5], putting forward the idea of IoT assurance driven by a *holistic view* of the target IoT system. Our approach defines and executes assurance evaluations matching and exploiting the architecture of the target system, distributing and aggregating computation accordingly. It considers the whole system lifecycle, and produces results at different granularity according to punctual as well as novel artificial intelligence-based evaluations. This approach enables the assessment of the system as a whole still considering its peculiarities, with negligible interference with the system working.

The contribution of this paper is twofold. We first define our novel approach for IoT assurance driven by artificial intelligence, focusing both on the methodological and on the technological point of view. We then present an experimental evaluation thereof in a real-world IoT system.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II discusses the state of the art of security assurance. Section III presents our approach for an effective IoT assurance. Section IV introduces a refinement of our previous assurance framework in [5] to support this novel paradigm. Section V includes an initial experimental evaluation of our approach. Finally, Section VI draws our conclusions.

II. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATIONS

We consider modern three-tiered IoT systems, where resource-constrained devices collect data and operate on the field; these devices are controlled with low latency by one or more edge nodes, whose computational power vary from medium-sized servers to microcontrollers; the overall business process is then analyzed and optimized at the cloud [9].

Security assurance is one of the means to assess the behavior of such systems to increase their trustworthiness [3]. An as-

assurance evaluation can be described at two levels: *i) assurance process*, that is, the (formal) description of the assurance evaluation; *ii) assurance framework*, that is, the implementation of the assurance process [10]. In particular, assurance processes for IoT mainly revolve around vertical aspects. Compliance to CIA requirements is still the focus of the state of the art, such as the assessment frameworks in [6], [11], the assurance framework in [7], the integrity of the software installed on edge nodes [8], the quality of service [12], the absence of vulnerabilities or weaknesses [13]. Risk-based approaches have also been proposed, such as [14], [15]. Finally, *assurance cases* are high-level objectives supported by evidence prepared by the system developers [16]. They have been successfully applied in self-adaptive systems [17], [18], and the research community is investigating their adoption for IoT assurance as well [9], [19], [20]. Assurance frameworks are typically strictly-coupled with the corresponding processes they implement, thus making difficult to reuse the same flexible implementation for different processes [5].

In short, current approaches for security assurance in IoT systems are not generic enough, limiting their evaluations to specific aspects of the target systems. In turn, this hinders the applicability of assurance in the real world. An effective evaluation requires instead higher level processes with less formalisms than in the past, while corresponding assurance frameworks should be flexible enough to accommodate different requirements instantiated on different target systems.

III. ASSURANCE EVALUATION

An effective assurance evaluation for IoT must be *i) multi-layer*, *ii) multi-phase*, and *iii) holistic*, as follows.

A. Multi-Layer Evaluation

The three layers composing modern IoT systems have intrinsic differences from the functional and non-functional point of view. For instance, cloud and edge layers often rely on well-known and (partially) trusted providers. Instead, IoT devices are resource-constrained and *opaque*, that is, little is known about their internals. This makes it difficult to define a proper assurance process even at high level, and the corresponding results may be a false negative (e.g., the IoT device does not respond because it is busy, not because it is offline). For these reasons, we put forward the idea of *lightweight IoT assurance* in [5]: our assurance evaluations target IoT devices *indirectly*, and rely on the edge and cloud layers to infer the behavior of the IoT layer. We note that this typically translates into querying some metrics already offered by the edge layer (as discussed in Section V), and the goal is to evaluate the target system as a whole, rather than individual nodes. In addition, we note that traditional and well-known assurance evaluations can still be used against the cloud layer [3].

B. Multi-Phase Evaluation

Edge and cloud layers are increasingly developed using approaches such as DevOps [21], and operated with orchestration platforms such as *Kubernetes*. In this scenario, development

artifacts become part of the system artifacts, for instance, continuous delivery pipelines and *Kubernetes* deployment files (i.e., *manifests*). These development artifacts describe the complete system deployment, and therefore become relevant for assurance, in terms of requirements to verify at run time, and of targets of evaluation. For instance, an assurance evaluation for *availability* can be executed against the manifest looking for High-Availability policies, in addition or in replacement of being executed against the system [22]. This brings crucial advantages when the system cannot be assessed directly (e.g., because of resource constraints), and constitutes a complementary and less-invasive means of evaluation.

C. Holistic Evaluation

The dynamic boundaries and complex interactions of IoT imply that rigid modeling of assurance processes (e.g., in terms of non-functional properties [23]) is no longer viable. Instead, assurance processes must rely more on the *behavioral analysis* of the target system to build an *holistic view* thereof, relying on and adapting, for instance, solutions based on anomaly and intrusion detection. In this context, the literature points to high-accuracy solutions based on artificial intelligence (AI) [24], [25]. However, accuracy is not the only indicator that matters [26]; other aspects to consider include *explainability*, *robustness*, and *edge-readiness*, as detailed in the following.

Explainability refers to understanding the logic behind a prediction of an AI model (*local explainability*), or how the model works in general (*global explainability*) [27], [28], [29]. Explainability is fundamental to increase trust in AI in any domains [28], and is even more important in the assurance domain, where assurance evaluations can result in the release of certificates that, by definition, should be trusted [3]. Here, we require *local interpretability*, which can be achieved either by *i) white-box models*, that is, models explainable by definition, such as decision trees [28]; *ii) open black-box models*, that is, techniques explaining neural networks-based models such as *surrogate white-box models* [28]. Intuitively, solutions based on white-box models should be preferable, as they are also simpler. We note that explainable models [28] based on the paradigm of *attention* [30] are being explored in the context of intrusion detection (e.g., [31]) and could boost IoT as well. We finally note that explainability is related also to requirements such as law compliance, accountability, fairness [28], [29].

Robustness refers to the *resistance* of AI models against data poisoning and adversarial attacks [32]. In fact, models can be attacked at training time by injecting poisoned inputs in the training set, or at inference time by sending specially-crafted inputs. This scenario becomes even more serious when working in an adversarial setting [32]. The assurance scenario is in fact adversarial, for instance in terms of a target system wishing to be certified without supporting the corresponding requirements [33]. Here, we require *robustness to inference-time attacks*, assuming that the training set is under the control of the entity performing the assurance evaluation. Currently, the preferred method to achieve robustness is *adversarial*

Figure 2. Architecture of the lighting system.

tication is enabled between edge and IoT nodes, to ensure that only authorized IoT devices can connect to the edge nodes; *ii) Availability* checking that edge nodes and, indirectly, IoT nodes are healthy and stable; *iii) Manifest-Checker* checking adherence of Kubernetes manifests to best practices; *iv) Backend-Dependency* and *v) Frontend-Dependency* checking the dependencies of cloud and edge microservices, and of the dashboard respectively, looking for vulnerable libraries; *vi) Image-Scanner* checking the *images* of the microservices, looking for vulnerable software. The probes are executed periodically, with interval varying according to their purpose, from 1 minute for *Availability* to automatic CI/CD triggers for *Manifest-Checker*, *Backend-Dependency*, *Frontend-Dependency*, and *Image-Scanner*. We chose these probes to maximize coverage and diversity. Probes *Robust-TLS* and *Availability* evaluate the target system at different layers, exploiting the edge layer to infer information on the IoT layer (*multi-layer evaluation* in Section III-A). Such probes also cover the *execution* phase of the system lifecycle, while the remaining probes cover the preceding phases, that is, development and deployment (*multi-phase evaluation* in Section III-B). In addition, *Availability* partially covers *holistic evaluation* in Section III-C, despite not using any AI models.

Results. Table I shows a summary of the results, where column “Passed” indicates the Boolean result of the evaluation, and column “Reason” indicates why the evaluation succeeded or failed (Section IV). Altogether, these evaluations show that the security of the lighting system is lacking, with only 1 out of 6 being successful. They also show that there is no much discrepancy between development, deployment, and execution time. In fact, only one execution-time probe successfully concluded (*Availability*), while all development and deployment-time probes concluded with a negative result.

Table II(a) shows an excerpt of the issues found in the manifests by *Manifest-Checker*, in percentage over the number

Table I
SUMMARY OF EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Probe	Passed	Reason
<i>Robust-TLS</i>	✗	Mutual TLS is configured
<i>Availability</i>	✓	System and its node always up
<i>Manifest-Checker</i>	✗	377/1904 sub-checks failed
<i>Backend-Dependency</i>	✗	22 vulnerabilities found
<i>Frontend-Dependency</i>	✗	20 vulnerabilities found
<i>Image-Scanner</i>	✗	165 vulnerabilities found

Table II
EXCERPT OF RESULTS OF PROBES MANIFEST-CHECKER AND BACKEND-DEPENDENCY

Issue	N. of findings (%)
<i>AppArmor</i> and <i>Seccomp Any</i>	100
<i>No CPU</i> and <i>Memory Limit</i>	100
<i>No CPU</i> and <i>Memory Requests</i>	89

(a) *Manifest-Checker*

Severity	N. of findings
High	3
Medium	19

(b) *Backend-Dependency*

of pods. In particular, *AppArmor Any* and *Seccomp Any* mean that all pods’ containers do not have any restrictions to resources and system calls, respectively, therefore having a large attack surface. *No CPU* and *Memory Limit* mean that all pods do not have any upper bounds on the CPU and memory they can use, eventually exhausting the system. *No CPU* and *Memory Requests* mean that most of the pods do not have any lower bounds on the CPU and memory they are assigned with, eventually not being able to complete their computation.

Table II(b) shows the number of vulnerabilities found by *Backend-Dependency*, categorized according to the CWE score (a community-driven list of software and hardware weaknesses). In particular, the probe revealed 3 vulnerabilities with *high* severity, referred to a weak pseudorandom number generator and to a possible incorrect TLS configuration. Although these vulnerabilities might not be a problem in practice, they are still indicators of a weak security posture.

Discussion. From the above results, it emerges that a holistic approach for security assurance in IoT systems is needed. An assessment based on a limited and traditional range of threats does not provide a complete security perspective. A comprehensive assessment must instead encompass the complete system lifecycle, inspecting also development and deployment artifacts. This approach is non-invasive with respect to runtime evaluation, and can uncover issues earlier. For instance, our experiments uncovered several relevant issues without stressing the system execution. In this context, DevSecOps stands out as a cornerstone, to the point that assurance evaluations *can* become a part of a DevSecOps pipeline [22]. At the same time, the system must be evaluated at all layers, possibly exploiting the edge layer to (indirectly) assess IoT nodes without impacting on their resources.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Modern IoT systems promise unmatched benefits to our lives, yet they are perceived as unsafe and untrustworthy. To address this gap and fully unleash their potential, security assurance must be redesigned towards less rigid and static solutions. The approach in this paper provides a first boost in this direction, proposing an assurance evaluation based on multi-layer, multi-phase, and behavioral activities. As a future work, we aim to put more emphasis on the latter, evaluating AI models matching the posed requirements.

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